

IDEA: Integrating Diversity in Evaluation and Assessment of Researchers – Experiences from Amsterdam

Workshop 2 - live workshop
Mapping diversity along career trajectory

Introduction

- Short round of introduction
 - Name
 - Role
 - What you found striking about the infographic
 - Any questions

IDEA Project Aim

Develop an **action plan** on how to **integrate researcher diversity** in the researcher assessment reforms taking place in **the R&R program** at the VU, using generative design co-creation methodology consisting of **4 workshops**.

Q1
Jan-
March

Map of intersection –
diversity issues and
researcher assessment

Q3
Jul-Sep

Final draft of action plan

Workshop 1

Workshop 2

Workshop 3

Workshop 4

Inventory of strategies

Q2
Apr-Jun

First draft of action plan

Q4
Oct-Dec

FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THE LEAKY PIPELINE PHENOMENON

	Factors	Suggestion solutions
1	Lack of clear and transparent promotion criteria	Transparent, unambiguous and well-communicated promotion criteria
2	Disproportionally high workloads of invisible service work	Equal distribution of labor
3	Sexism and racial discrimination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acknowledge identity in knowledge production over 'objectivity' • Promote inclusivity, diversity, and equity through policies and trainings, and monitor • Role models
4	Exclusion from professional and support networks	Culturally competent mentorship
5	Precarious working conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for parents and caretakers • Do not expect uniform productivity
6	Lack of (financial) support for engaging in true research interests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide growth possibilities • Reward and value research on diversity, equity and inclusion

QUESTIONS TO EXPLORE

2

- How attractive is VU as an employer for different demographic and professional groups?
- Will the proposed changes meaningfully impact the balance between valuing teaching and research?
- To what extent do ambiguous promotion criteria pose a barrier to achieving diversity?
- How do current criteria limit mobility and interdisciplinarity within VU?
- Why is there no specific targeting of PhD candidates or Team Science initiatives, and what are the implications?

Analysis faculty plans

MAPPING DIVERSITY WITHIN FACULTY POLICIES

This workshop

Goal: create **map** of career trajectory and where on it opportunities and threats for diversity lie

In terms of privacy

- We will use anonymized data from the workshops – nothing linking to personal information
- Please do not put information on boards/slides which are personal
- We are not taking notes - please put all input on slides

Some ground rules

- *You are in charge of content, we guide the process*
- *Listen to each other (no talking over) and be cordial*
- *Both experiential and content expertise is welcome and appreciated*
- *Goal is not necessarily to agree, but to lead to deeper understanding*
- *Any others from your side?*

Exercise 1: Career trajectories

Individually, reflect on and visualize your own career trajectory or that of someone you know who meets IDEA's target group (15 minutes).

1. Pick one of the formats here or draw your own
2. Add important considerations

Exercise 1: Career trajectories

1. Share your individual reflections
2. Select one template/format/career trajectory map to continue working with in the next exercise

Career trajectory

① Scientific research / publications

+

② teaching classes (availability) ↔ if not teaching, what other projects are you involved in which contributes to the work you have done (for example diversity projects)

yearly / annual reviews with your manager.

→ Compare it with the criteria for promotions.

- what are these criteria? are these available / transparent.

- how many researchers are qualified or eligible for this? 10-15-5 people yearly?

- who will from management team actively stand for this researcher and promote his/her achievement so they make a chance to get promotions? You can't nominate yourself for this so who will do this for you? will this person be your active promoter? Do you have to search for this yourself? is this always your manager?

+

③ → Also what if you get pregnant and aren't able to teach or do research?

→ what criteria will be taken into account.

→ are you able to make promotions if you didn't teach / do research?

Needs financial stability and awareness on research careers

1. Bachelor in
2. Master in
3. PhD in

Field blocked out; country outside Europe blocked out

Field blocked out; (NL)

Field blocked out; (NL)

Position blocked out

} Difficulties with funding, immigration
} " "

?

30% PhDs international but most policies are by Dutch people

Influences

- immigration (staying in NL but also moving abroad for postdoc)
- language barriers (only some jobs possible)
- commitment to family obligations

- ↳ No sponsored Dutch language training
- ↳ Minimal integration support

↳ social isolation, difficulty navigating systems in a new country

- Application for P.I.D. - Position: ^{1st gen.} Less 'study success'
 - less previous mentoring/support
 - often an DE1 themes/programmes (sensitive to socio-cultural changes of Nat. Wksh. agenda)

- SES influence on period abroad, conferencing etc
 - PhD trajectory: - combination with care duties, financial support of family, extra health care costs, etc.
 - extra burden of DE1-related services & teaching (committees, outreach)
 - am. levels: sexism etc. weight in (1st) authorship challenges, diminished formal acceptance with female/ 'exotic' names

- Academic output: fewer invitations & citations

- Postdoc: more challenging with early family/marriage
 - financial (central) support may be lacking
 - mentoring/networking support
 - risk of isolation abroad - not part of network etc.
 → as a result, research output is under threat
 - annual conversation with P.I who also finances position, instead of independent supervision

Cases

Exercise 2: Critical moments for diversity

1. Individually, add ideas about critical moments for diversity in the chosen map/template/format
2. Discuss all the ideas

Closing

- Next steps: processing of input (also with input from workshop on May 22) to finalize a map of critical moments for diversity in researcher evaluations
- Last input from you: what is 1 thing we should keep in mind for the rest of the project?